

The HEFTIE project

Handling Enormous Files from Tomography Imaging Experiments

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Abstract

X-ray tomography is a technique used across diverse scientific fields, such as material sciences, geosciences, palaeontology, and life sciences. With modern experiments generating enormous datasets, the development of ‘chunked’ file formats - which break down massive files into smaller parts - has become essential for data processing. The HEFTIE project aimed to significantly improve tools and educational resources for handling such datasets. In this short article we describe the new resources and tools we created as part of the HEFTIE project.

1. INTRODUCTION

X-ray tomography produces extremely large datasets, often exceeding 1 terabyte in size, which are too large to fit into standard computer memory. A prime example of this is data in the Human Organ Atlas, which provides a total of over 100 terabytes (and counting) of images (Walsh et al., 2025). As an example, [Figure 1](#) shows a rendering of a 3D image of a single colon that is 1080 gigabytes (1.08 terabytes) in total data size.

Published Feb 09, 2026

Acknowledgements

HEFTIE was funded by the [OSCARS project](#), which has received funding from the European Commission’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751.

Thanks to Alessandro Felder for reviewing and providing helpful improvements and comments for the HEFTIE textbook.

Figure 1: Rendering of a 3D image of a colon, taken from the Human Organ Atlas. Raw data available from Human Organ Atlas Collaboration *et al.* (2025).

This abundance of data has led to the adoption of ‘chunked’ file formats, enabling scientists to process these datasets in manageable portions. However, many researchers lack the tools and training to work with such massive data effectively, which slows down analysis and limits the scientific discoveries that could be made from this data.

To tackle these issues, we undertook a project called *Handling Enormous Files from Tomography Imaging Experiments*, or HEFTIE for short. We aimed to develop a comprehensive digital textbook and new software tools for working with chunked 3D imaging datasets. In this short article we give an overview of chunked data formats, and the new resources we created as part of the HEFTIE projects to help scientists work with them.

2. CHUNKED FILE FORMATS

A simple way to store 3D imaging data is to save it as a series of individual 2D images (often called a *stack* of individual *slices*). As an example, if we have an image with shape $(10, 10, 20)$, we could save it to 20 2D image files, each of which has shape $(10, 10)$. This is illustrated in [Figure 2](#). One way of thinking about this is that we are

splitting the 3D image up into chunks, and each chunk is saved to a single file. In this case each chunk has shape $(n_x, n_y, 1)$, where n_x and n_y are the size of the 3D image in the x- and y- dimensions. If we want to fetch a small cube of data from this 3D image, say shape $(2, 2, 2)$, then we have to read and de-compress the two image files that contain this data, but then throw away most of the two $(10, 10)$ shaped images that we've read in.

Image shape = $(10, 10, 20)$
Chunk shape = $(10, 10, 1)$

Figure 2: Splitting a 3D image into slices. Each colour represents a separate slice saved to a 2D image file.

Image shape = (10, 10, 20)
 Chunk shape = (2, 2, 3)

Figure 3: Splitting a 3D image into chunks. Each colour represents a separate chunk saved to a file.

Instead of splitting up the image into slices, each of which have a size of 1 along the third dimension, we could instead split the image up into different sized *chunks*. Each chunk represents a single file saved to disk. This is illustrated in [Figure 3](#)

Splitting up a large image into different chunks was one of the original motivations for developing Zarr array storage format¹. Zarr allows arbitrary array data (which includes images) to be saved into individual chunks, and each chunk can be compressed for space savings.

For really large images, zooming out and viewing the whole field of view of the image would require loading every pixel, which might not be possible on low memory computers. If lower resolution copies of the data are computed and stored alongside the original image, this problem can be solved by progressively loading higher and higher resolution data as you zoom in (like zooming in from the whole

¹<https://zarr.dev>, <https://zarr-specs.readthedocs.io>

planet to a single street on an interactive map). Storing multi-resolution copies of the image is the basis of the OME-Zarr data format (Moore et al., 2023), which builds on top of Zarr.

OME-Zarr is designed to enable efficient visualisation and processing of huge imaging datasets. It excels at this, but the cost of using this next generation file format is added complexity when creating these datasets. In the HEFTIE project we developed tools and training to address this complexity gap, hopefully making it easier for scientists to produce and consume OME-Zarr data.

3. PROJECT OUTCOMES

3.a. Digital textbook

We created the HEFTIE textbook (Stansby et al., 2025), which explains the theory and practice behind handling large bio-imaging datasets using the OME-Zarr data format. Code examples are used throughout the textbook to illustrate concepts, written in the Python programming language² and put together using the Jupyter Book document system³. The textbook is freely available and licensed under a permissive license, allowing others to adapt and remix the work.

3.b. Compressor benchmarking

When creating Zarr arrays there are many different configuration options to choose from, including chunk size, compression algorithm, and configuration options for each compression algorithm. To help scientists navigate the large number of available options we developed a benchmark suite to measure how well different sets of compressor parameters perform when reading and writing data (Meechan et al., 2025). These benchmarks and the code to run them are freely available and licensed under a permissive license, allowing others to adapt and remix the work. A sample figure from the benchmarking report is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: A sample figure from the HEFTIE benchmarking report. Taken from Meechan et al. (2025).

²<https://www.python.org>

³<https://jupyterbook.org>

3.c. Tools for working with Zarr

We made a number of improvements and feature requests to the *zarr-python* software library⁴ and related software to make it more user friendly, including:

- A command line interface for converting Zarr v2 array metadata to Zarr v3 array metadata⁵.
- Automatic data caching⁶.
- Improved documentation^{7,8,9}.
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3.d. 3D visualisation and annotation

We added new features and made a number of improvements to the webknossos web-based visualisation software¹⁰, specifically targeted towards working with 3D imaging data. These improvements included:

- Evaluating and implementing a quick-select feature for 3D annotation based on *Segment Anything 2* (Ravi *et al.*, 2024).
- Rotation of the 2D views in arbitrary planes to better show 3D structure that do not align well with the array axes.
- Selective segment visibility to allow visualisation of a custom set of annotations (for example, in a whole body annotation this could be used to change the organs being visualised).
- key-value metadata fields for segments and skeleton trees to allow additional metadata (e.g., image intensity) to be stored as part of these data structures and used in downstream analysis.

4. CONCLUSION

During the HEFTIE project we successfully developed a new digital textbook and new software tools for working with chunked 3D imaging datasets. We hope that these resources provide a useful resource for scientists working with huge imaging data. By making all our outputs openly accessible we hope that they will continue to be developed in the future, both by ourselves and others wishing to contribute.

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⁴<https://zarr.readthedocs.io>

⁵[zarr-developers/zarr-python#3257](https://github.com/zarr-developers/zarr-python#3257)

⁶[zarr-developers/zarr-python#3366](https://github.com/zarr-developers/zarr-python#3366)

⁷[dask/dask-image#407](https://github.com/dask/dask-image#407)

⁸[scikit-image/scikit-image#7879](https://github.com/scikit-image/scikit-image#7879)

⁹[zarr-developers/zarr-python#3480](https://github.com/zarr-developers/zarr-python#3480)

¹⁰<https://webknossos.org>

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